

Comparison of the Effectiveness of Several Antiseptic Mouthwashes in Reducing Respiratory and Upper Digestive Symptoms in COVID-19 Patients: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

COVID-19 is a respiratory infection outbreak caused by SARS-CoV-2. COVID-19 is primarily transmitted through respiratory droplets, which are abundant in mucous membranes, particularly in the patient's oral cavity. Coughing, impaired smell and taste, and shortness of breath are common symptoms of infection. Antiseptic mouthwash with an action mechanism consistent with SARS-CoV-2 virology can reduce the virus's pathogenicity in the oral cavity. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of antiseptic mouthwash in reducing respiratory and upper digestive symptoms in COVID-19 patients. This study used a systematic review method with reference to PRISMA 2020. From May to July 2023, a literature search was conducted in the PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Scopus databases. The article's relevance was determined by the findings of RCT or CT studies on the effectiveness of PVP-I, H₂O₂, and CHX mouthwashes in the oral cavity of COVID-19 patients, which is characterized by a reduction in the symptoms they suffer. Non-experimental study designs were excluded. The CONSORT 2010 checklist was used to assess the risk of article inclusion bias. Four research articles with a total of 299 subjects were deemed relevant to the inclusion criteria. As many as two out of every four articles demonstrated high research quality. The most common COVID-19 symptoms reported by patients were non-productive cough symptoms (n = 117). PVP-I and H₂O₂ mouthwashes at concentrations of 0,5% and 1% were used as study samples. The two drugs were able to accelerate the recovery of dyspnea, non-productive cough, and ageusia with a maximum of 14-day treatment period. Ultimately, the research shows that the recovery of COVID-19 patients with symptoms of non-productive cough, dyspnea, and ageusia can be aided by using an antiseptic mouthwash containing PVP-I or H₂O₂ but in the appropriate concentration, duration, and frequency of the drug.

Introduction

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is the latest respiratory infection outbreak caused by a Coronavirus after its emergence in 2002 taking the form of the SARS-CoV phenotype [1]. Recently, on May 5th, 2023, the World Health Organization (WHO) determined the

status of COVID-19 is no longer a global health issue [2]. The Indonesian government downgraded the status of the COVID-19 pandemic to an endemic on 21 June 2023 in response to the global decision of WHO [3]. Reporting from the Kompas website, this decision was taken given the results of a government survey carried

More Information

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out on an ongoing basis by the Ministry of Health (Kemenkes), Ministry of Home Affairs (Kemendagri), as well as experts from various universities in Indonesia, which show that 99 percent of Indonesians have COVID-19 antibodies [3]. The number of confirmed cases in Indonesia to date is 6.8 million cases with a case fatality rate (CFR) of 2.38 percent [4].

Coronavirus (CoV) is a single-stranded positive-sense RNA virus [1,5]. This virus belongs to the coronavirinae subfamily and has 4 genera, namely alphacoronavirus (alpha-CoV), betacoronavirus (beta-CoV), deltacoronavirus (delta-CoV), and gammacoronavirus (gamma-CoV) [1,5,50]. CoV strains that are pathogenic to humans (h-CoV) belong in the alpha-CoV and beta-CoV types [5]. The beta-CoV genus involving SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV strains is the result of genome sequencing analysis regarding the CoV genus and its relationship to upper respiratory tract infections. The International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV) determined the development of the name of the COVID-19 pathogenic virus to become SARS-CoV-2 because of its resemblance to SARS-CoV [5]. As a zoonotic virus, the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 began with *Rhinolopus affinis* (bats) and *Manis javanica* (pangolins) as intermediate hosts to humans [1,6]. On 18 December 2019, the first suspected case of COVID-19 was reported in a hospital in the Wuhan region of China, where 5 patients had acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). After further observation, this incident confirmed the pattern of cross-species transmission of COVID-19 to be human-to-human [1,5]. SARS-CoV-2 spreads faster than its predecessor upper respiratory tract infection viruses (ARI), SARS-CoV, and MERS-CoV when compared to the standard reproduction number (R_0) [7,8]. At the beginning of 2020, the R_0 prediction for SARS-CoV-2 based on WHO estimates was in the range of 2.0-2.5 [8]. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) also issued an estimated range for R_0 COVID-19, ranging from 3.8-8.9, exceeding data available from WHO. The results of research by Yu et al. (2020) support the validity of this data and explain further the R_0 findings of several European countries, namely the United Kingdom, France, and Germany, which rank highest with values of 6.94, 6.32, and 6.07 [9]. The primary mode of transmission of SARS-CoV-2 is through respiratory droplets [53] produced by individuals who are infected with symptoms (symptomatic) and those who are not (asymptomatic) [7,8]. Daily activities, such as talking, sneezing, or coughing, if carried out by an infected individual will produce droplets that eventually settle in the air [1,2]. The degrees of heat and humidity of droplets prolong the presence of droplets in the air thereby increasing the possibility of droplets sticking to surfaces and virus particles being carried by individuals who are asymptomatic [1,6,8].

The theoretical basis for research in the field of dentistry in the first and second years of the COVID-19 outbreak circulated in findings regarding the role of the oral cavity as a viral entry pathway for SARS-CoV-2 [8,10]. Functionally, SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV have similarities in their interaction with host cell receptors, namely by recognizing human angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) [5]. Xu et al. (2020) found an abundance of hACE2 in the epithelial cells of the oral cavity through his research [10]. In 10 of the 32 samples of normal oral tissue obtained by Xu et al. (2020), the highest average expression of hACE2 in the oral cavity was recorded on the tongue compared to the floor of the mouth [10]. Another research outcome is that ACE2 is not only found in epithelial cells, but also in other cells of the oral cavity, such as B and T lymphocyte cells, and fibroblasts [10]. The life cycle of SARS-CoV-2 begins with binding action between the binding receptor domain (RBD) of S protein and ACE2 followed by the endocytosis stage, which includes attachment and viral cellular fusion of the virus [5,8]. This process is assisted by the subunits of the S protein, namely subunit 1 (S1) and subunit 2 (S2) [5,8]. The activation of viral subunits is mediated by a protease enzyme coded genetically as transmembrane protease serine-2 (TMPRSS2) [8]. Access to SARS-CoV-2 by ACE2 correlates with viral load, a marker of the severity of COVID-19 infection [11]. Like ACE2, viral load has high levels in the oral cavity as a structure of the oronasopharynx complex [5,11].

A significant increase in viral load indicates the onset of symptoms of COVID-19 [11]. Symptoms of COVID-19 are multiple and vary widely in their distribution [51]. Research conducted by Guan et al. (2020) found that most patients had at least 7 symptoms of COVID-19, namely fever (83-99%), cough (59-82%), fatigue (44-70%), anorexia (40-84%), shortness of breath (31-40%), sputum production (28-33%) and myalgia (11-35%) [52] manifest in the early stages of infection and are reported to be reversible after recovery [5]. The median incubation period for COVID-19, i.e. the span between the first exposure and the onset of symptoms, is estimated to be between 4 and 7 days, with a maximum possible incubation duration of 14 days [7,12,13]. In general, the effectiveness of a drug is the degree to which the drug's mechanism of action achieves the desired result under normal circumstances [14]. A drug is effective by observing a measurable increase in the patient's clinical signs and symptoms [15]. The orientation for using oral antiseptics, including antiseptic mouthwashes, is patient-centered and conducted at two levels: (1) reducing the severity of COVID-19 symptoms, and (2) reducing the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 [11,16,17]. If properly administered and prescribed to patients with COVID-19, the level of salivary viral load will decrease, as well as the severity

of COVID-19 [18]. The recommendations of mouthwash for pre-procedure dentistry issued by the American Dental Association (ADA) and the American Association of Endodontics (AAE) are 0.2% povidone-iodine (PVP-I) and 1% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) [19]. An article by Yoon et al. (2020) found a description of the cationic effect of chlorhexidine (CHX) which was able to reduce the viral load of SARS-CoV-2 in the oral cavity [20,21]. In this article, we conducted a search through the PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Scopus databases to find original articles resulting from randomized control trial (RCT) and clinical trials (CT) studies on antiseptic mouthwash in relation to the therapeutic effects produced to accelerate the recovery of symptoms in COVID-19 patients. We extract the data and present it in a comparison table. Based on the data and explanation above, the authors created a research plan to evaluate the comparative effectiveness of several antiseptic mouthwashes to reduce respiratory and upper digestive symptoms in COVID-19 patients. We hope that the result of this research can be used as reference material for theory development in the scientific field of dentistry and by health workers to assist patients and the public in recognizing the risk of COVID-19 symptoms and minimizing the duration of these symptoms to speed up the recovery process.

Materials and Methods

Registration and Protocol

This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines [22]. We report our findings to be adapted with the "PRISMA 2020 expanded 27-item checklist" and the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions. The protocol of this study is registered in PROSPERO (ID = CRD42023445286) [23,24].

Identifying Research Questions

The research frame of reference is based on the research question "how is the effectiveness of several antiseptic mouthwashes compared to reducing respiratory and upper digestive symptoms in COVID-19 patients?" and follows the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome) format, which is as follows: (1) Population: COVID-19 patients; (2) Intervention: antiseptic mouthwash containing PVP-I, H₂O₂, or CHX at any concentration given with any frequency or dose to COVID-19 patients; (3) Comparison: other antiseptic mouthwashes with ingredients other than PVP-I, H₂O₂, CHX, standard COVID-19 drugs, and placebo; (4) Outcome: Decreased duration of respiratory symptoms (anosmia, non-productive cough, and dyspnea) and upper digestive disorders (ageusia) and in COVID-19 patients [22].

Search Strategy

A literature search was conducted through the PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Scopus databases using

the advanced search feature with a combination of keywords ("SARS-CoV-2" OR "COVID-19" OR "Coronavirus") AND ("Antiseptic" OR "Povidone-iodine" OR "Hydrogen peroxide" OR "Chlorhexidine") AND ("Mouth wash" OR "Mouth rinse" OR "Gargle") AND ("Effectiveness") OR ("Gustatory" OR "Olfactory" OR "Respiratory" OR "Digestive"). Moreover, additional literature searches were carried out manually by hand-searching which were deemed relevant and eligible for this study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Articles included in this study were experimental reports regarding the efficiency of PVP-I, H₂O₂, or CHX antiseptic mouthwash in the oral cavity of COVID-19 patients with a randomized control trial and clinical trial study design. The efficiency of the antiseptic mouthwash was measured by the improvement or decrease in the recovery of the patient's respiratory and upper digestive symptoms and clinical signs, including anosmia, non-productive cough, dyspnea, and ageusia. Furthermore, the articles should be available in full-text and published by reputable journals within the last 3 years (2020-2023). Exclusion criteria for this study were articles reporting the effects of non-antiseptic mouthwash in COVID-19 patients and/or with non-experimental study designs, for example, case studies, surveys, cross-sectional, cohort, and case-control.

Study Selection

A literature review was carried out by one reviewer (S.L.S.) on the PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Scopus databases using the specified combination of specific keywords. Articles from the results page are saved and then exported to the website Rayyan (<http://rayyan.qcri.org> (accessed on June 9th, 2023)) to identify duplicate articles. The process of screening articles based on the PRISMA 2020 flowchart is done by checking the relevance of the title or abstract of the article to the inclusion criteria and removing irrelevant articles (exclusion). The respective slicing is a full-text availability analysis of articles that match the inclusion criteria, including articles found by hand searching, and excludes articles that could not be accessed in full. The full text of the selected studies in the screening was recovered and put into reference manager software, Mendeley (<https://www.mendeley.com> (accessed on June 9th, 2023)). A number of articles would be obtained and subjected to a study quality assessment before being analyzed and synthesized into tabular form to answer research questions. The final stage of study selection is to discuss the findings of the review with experts (D.Z. and N.N.) in order to obtain research feedback [15].

Quality Assessment

The Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) checklist was used to assess the quality of

randomized controlled trial (RCT) and clinical trial (CT) studies in this investigation. The adoption of CONSORT significantly impacts the presentation of RCT reports, particularly in research involving human trials (in-person). This type of research is common in dentistry, dermatology, and ophthalmology. The CONSORT checklist has 25 items that address study design reporting, analysis, and interpretation of an RCT.

Data Extraction and Analysis

The data and information gathered in this study will be organized into two analysis tables: (Table 1) baseline characteristics, clinical conditions (comorbid diseases, history of contact with a person with a positive diagnosis of COVID-19) of the patient, and respiratory and upper digestive symptoms related to COVID-19 (anosmia, non-productive cough, dyspnea, and ageusia); (Table 2) the type of mouth rinse, concentration, dosage, duration of use, drug frequency, and the distribution of the degree of reduction in COVID-19 symptoms that has been mentioned, as well as the details of the observation days and the p-value of each symptom to determine the significance of the intervention. Other supporting data is provided in the appendices: (Appendix A) general characteristics of the research sample; (Appendix B) evaluation of study quality using the CONSORT 2010 checklist. If any discrepancies arise during this stage, researchers will discuss to resolve them.

Results

The search process in the databases yielded a total of 4343 articles (Pubmed = 3850; ScienceDirect = 326; Scopus = 172). Prior to the screening stage, the sources of the article were filtered by removing up to 36 articles that were identified as duplicate articles. The screening stage, which involved analyzing the titles and abstracts of 4307 articles, identified 4262 that had to be eliminated because they were irrelevant to the topic and purpose of this study. The second screening stage identified the contents of the article in full-text, and 9 articles were eliminated since we were unable to download it. The final article sources were selected by analyzing the entirety of the text. Nine articles were eliminated because (1) 6 articles included research on the effects of non-antiseptic mouthwash in COVID-19 patients; (2) 1 article is a non-experimental study; and (3) 20 articles included studies that did not include reduction of respiratory and upper gastrointestinal symptoms in COVID-19 patients. An additional manual search using the hand-search method was conducted, yielding 1 article relevant to the research question. As a result, two randomized controlled trial articles and two randomized clinical trial articles could be analyzed and synthesized. Figure 1 (Appendix C) depicts the

mapping of the results of a literature search through a database with reference to the PRISMA 2020 chart.

Table 1 (Appendix D) displays data on the characteristics of the research subjects in the included studies. (1) sociodemographic variables, including gender (male/female), the patient's age range, comorbid illnesses (respiratory, diabetes, hypertension), and a history of close contact with a person diagnosed positively with COVID-19; and (2) basic clinical variables (anosmia, non-productive cough, dyspnea, ageusia). The number in the table represents the total number of patients in both the intervention and control groups. Men are the most frequently studied subjects in three out of four articles. When recruiting patients, the most common comorbid disease was hypertension, with 31 people counted from three articles.

Table 2 (Appendix E) displays data on the distribution of the reduction rate in respiratory and upper digestive symptoms related to COVID-19 obtained from patient complaints during the patient recruitment process. The treatment period varies in each article, ranging from 1 week ($n = 2$) to ± 2 weeks ($n = 2$). There was 1 article that did not include dyspnea (breathing difficulties) in the study. The decrease in the patient's respiratory symptoms is characterized by a reduction of the percentage of symptoms evaluated from initial observation (day 0) to final observation (day 6/7/14/21) which means the patient is recovering.

Discussion

The total ratio of male ($n = 189$) and female ($n = 110$) patients studied in this study's inclusion articles is estimated to be close to 1.9:1, with the majority of infected patients aged 30-49 years. Gender and age have a significant influence on a person's proclivity to become infected with COVID-19 [29-31]. According to Meister et al. (2022)'s cohort study, women are less likely than men to contract COVID-19 [32]. It is explained further in that study about women's protective effect against COVID-19, which will increase as the disease's severity increases [32]. This finding is consistent with the fact that women have more estrogen, which inhibits the activity of renin-angiotensin system components (RAS) [33]. Estrogen will control the expression of ACE2 as an essential RAS enzyme [33]. Female patients will consequently have better COVID-19 outcomes and lower mortality rates than men [33]. In men, particularly elderly patients over 55 years of age, ACE2 that is not properly regulated can map the condition, and the demographics of these patients are the top risk factors for COVID-19 [34].

The four inclusion articles investigated the symptoms of anosmia, non-productive cough, dyspnea, and ageusia, making these four symptoms the study's dependent variable. As per Grant et al. (2020)'s findings, COVID-19 patients will exhibit more complex

clinical symptoms in the oronasopharynx and oral cavity complex, such as productive and non-productive cough, olfactory disturbances (hyposmia/anosmia), difficulty breathing (dyspnea), and impaired taste perception (hypogeusia/dysgeusia/ageusia) [35,36]. Apart from respiratory and upper digestive symptoms, several patients had comorbid diseases such as hypertension (n = 31), diabetes (n = 17), and respiration (n = 7). At least two out of the three comorbidities commonly found in COVID-19 patients are hypertension and diabetes [36]. The link between the disease and the patient's susceptibility to COVID-19 can be traced back to the molecular level, specifically ACE2. Fang et al. (2020) concluded from their research that hypertensive patients tend to worsen with a poor prognosis when infected with COVID-19 [37].

There were three articles found with reports on the effects of PVP-I mouthwash with solution concentrations of 0.5 and 1.0% on symptom relief in COVID-19 patients [26-28]. Mouthwashes were administered with other accompanying drugs, such as PVP-I pulverization into syringes, PVP-I ointment, and iota-carrageenan (IC) nasal sprays, among eligible PVP-I articles (n = 2) [26,28]. PVP-I is regarded as an ideal antiseptic because it does not cause irritation, toxicity, or staining and has a long-lasting microbicidal action in the oral cavity [18,39]. Iodine (I₂) and a soluble carrier polymer, polyvinylpyrrolidone, make up the PVP-I complex [16,35]. To enter human cells, SARS-CoV-2 has a lipid envelope loaded with spike glycoproteins that form bonds with ACE2 [40]. In aqueous conditions, iodine released by PVP-I will penetrate microorganisms and oxidize essential proteins and nucleotides. This action would prevent SARS-CoV-2 from attaching to ACE2 and thus further hinder the virus from spreading to other organs in the body [19,40]. The antiviral properties of PVP-I are supported by the findings of an in vitro study conducted by Bidra et al. (2020), who discovered that mouthwashes containing 3.0%, 1.5%, and 1.0% PVP-I were effective in reducing SARS-CoV-2 infection at drug exposure durations of 15, 30, and 60 seconds [41]. Two studies were found to state a significant improvement in symptoms of non-productive cough, dyspnea, and ageusia, but not in symptoms of anosmia [26,28]. In the study by Chalageri et al. (2022), 24 of 73 patients (36.92%) with COVID-19 with non-productive cough symptoms who were given 0.5% PVP-I mouthwash intervention with gargling instructions 3 times a day for 30 seconds recovered within 9 days [26]. In a different study, led by Amtha et al. (2021), 1% PVP-I was shown to significantly accelerate the recovery of patients with non-productive cough (n = 23), dyspnea (n = 12), and ageusia (n = 20) within 14 days [28]. Patients were instructed to rinse their mouths with PVP-I 6 times a day. They were monitored on the eighth and

fourteenth days of the study. The study was completed by all patients, and there were no reports of interventional drug side effects.

Domênico et al. (2021) discovered that dyspnea was statistically significant after testing the effect of a mouthwash containing hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) on 193 participants [25]. On the eighth day, 11.34% of patients in the intervention group and 24.7% of patients in the control group reported a reduction in symptoms. However, patients in the intervention group did not have a statistically different time to clinical recovery when compared to the control group. H₂O₂ is another antiseptic that is frequently studied and thought to be effective against the SARS-CoV-2 viral load in the oral cavity [19]. The natural synthesis of H₂O₂ in the human body is a by-product of the oxygen metabolism process [35]. The substance H₂O₂ is then hydrolyzed by the enzymes peroxidase and catalase to form water (H₂O) and free oxygen ions (O₂) [35]. H₂O₂ damages lipid membranes and attacks the viral envelope by releasing oxygen-free radicals [35]. The use of 3% H₂O₂ and diluted 1-1.5% H₂O₂ has been shown to act as a defense mechanism against other SARS-CoV-2, particularly by inducing overexpression suppression of toll-like receptor 3 (TLR3) proteins, which will eventually reduce the rate of COVID-19 infection in the upper respiratory tract [35].

No articles that discussed the recovery of anosmia symptoms in COVID-19 patients were found. Anosmia is a type of quantitative olfactory dysfunction in which the patient's nose loses its ability to smell completely [42]. Odor perception is acquired through orthonasal (via sniffing) and retronasal (via the flow of exhaled air from the nasopharynx to the oropharynx. More than 1 million dendrites of olfactory receptor neurons (ORN) project to the nasal mucosa from the olfactory bulb (OB). Odors that reach the olfactory epithelium dissolve in the mucous layer, activating the olfactory receptors via complex interactions that frequently necessitate the use of odor-binding proteins. Olfactory sensory neurons convert chemical messages into nerve impulse emission frequencies and send them to the olfactory glomerulus (Glom). The olfactory bulb processes and integrates olfactory information. Non-neural cells such as support cells, stem cells, and perivascular cells, on the other hand, aid in the expression of specific odorant genes. Infection of these cells causes anosmia and other odor-perception abnormality in other patients. Anosmia was thought to be a side effect of drugs used intranasally in the early days of COVID-19 [43]. Through prospective research, anosmia was eventually recognized as a symptom of COVID-19 [43,44]. Mouthwash is a type of topical drug that has a local mechanism of action and is applied to patients in a relatively non-invasive manner [45]. According to the focus of this research, antiseptics are frequently used in

the form of mouthwashes to produce effects from the oral cavity to the oropharynx [45]. The use of mouthwash has had no therapeutic effect on anosmia, a disorder of smell perception in the nasal mucosa. Intranasal or systemic therapy is used for patients with anosmia, based on the drug dose and frequency, as well as the patient's age [44]. Aside from the therapeutic effect, the ingredients in mouthwash can occasionally cause adverse drug reactions (ADR) in patients, such as burning mouth and nose, oral pain, and tooth discoloration [45,46]. The presence of ADR is highlighted in Domênico et al. (2021)'s study, in which the patient reported that the administration of H₂O₂ mouthwash caused the throat and nose to burn (burning throat, burning nose) [25].

Reports of randomized control trials (RCT) or clinical trials (CT) on the effectiveness of chlorhexidine mouthwash (CHX) in COVID-19 patients, unfortunately, cannot be found even though we have expanded the area of the literature search to the clinicaltrials.gov website. The majority of research listed on the site is "completed" but no research results have been published and accessed. CHX is classified as a cationic strong antiseptic from the bisbiguanide group [11,46]. In bacteria and fungi, CHX salts, chlorhexidine gluconate (CHX-G), or chlorhexidine digluconate (CHX-DG) will dissociate and release its positively charged ions to react negatively charged bacteria [46]. A damaged bacterial membrane will make it easier for CHX to bind to phospholipids on the inner membrane, causing membrane leakage, and ejecting potassium ions (K⁺) out of the cell [46]. Bacterial cells will soon undergo lysis. 46 Different interactions occur between CHX and SARS-CoV-2. One of SARS-CoV-2's structural proteins, membrane protein (M), is positively charged [47]. When two similar charges meet, they create a repellent force caused by the direction of force with respect to each other [47,48]. CHX may cause ADR even at concentrations as low as 0.06% and 0.2% based on the risk-benefit analysis of drugs [46]. Research performed by Haydari et al. (2017) concluded that 65% and 21% of the CHX intervention group 0.06% and 0.2% experienced loneliness loss of taste [49]. The study stated there was a mild discoloration in patients in both, intervention and control, groups [49].

Conclusions

The use of 0.5% PVP-I mouthwash 3 and 6 times a day for 30 seconds can accelerate the recovery of non-productive cough symptoms in COVID-19 patients when compared to patients who do not receive any treatment. At a higher concentration, i.e. 1%, PVP-I mouthwash is able to act as a concomitant therapy for standard COVID-19 care to patients with symptoms of non-productive cough, dyspnea, and ageusia. Another mouthwash content that is considered effective against dyspnea symptoms is H₂O₂ with mouthwash

instructions 3 times a day. COVID-19 patients who were given H₂O₂ mouthwash intervention experienced a decrease in symptoms of no more than 6 days of therapy compared to control group patients who were given a placebo solution in the form of a mixture of distilled water and mint essence.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, S.L.S., D.Z., and N.N.; methodology, S.L.S., D.Z., and N.N.; software, S.L.S.; validation, D.Z. and N.N.; formal analysis, S.L.S., D.Z., and N.N.; investigation, S.L.S.; resources, S.L.S.; data curation, S.L.S., D.Z., N.N.; writing—original draft preparation, S.L.S.; writing—review and editing, S.L.S., D.Z., and N.N.; visualization, S.L.S., D.Z., and N.N.; supervision, D.Z. and N.N.; project administration, S.L.S., D.Z., and N.N. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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The data are contained within the article.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendixes

Appendix A

Table A1 features information about the general characteristics of the included research samples, such as the author's name, year of publication, country, article title, research design, and duration, number of patients, and COVID-19 criteria (examination techniques, swab types, and examination time span before being included in the study). According to the data acquired, there are two study articles from Asian countries, one from India and one from Indonesia. The remaining two articles are from Europe (France) and South America (Brazil). The grouping of article research designs used was 1: 1, with two randomized controlled trials and two others being randomized clinical trials.

Table A1: Characteristics of Research Samples Included in the Study

#	Author (yrs)	Country	Study title	Study design	Study duration (days)	Number of patients (pts)	COVID-19 testing	Type of swab	The time range for diagnosis of Covid-19 before research (h)
1.	Domênico et al. [25] (2021)	Brazil	Hydrogen peroxide as an auxiliary treatment for COVID-19 in Brazil: a randomized double-blind clinical trial	Randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial	8	193 I (n = 97)* C (n = 96)*	RT-PCR	Nasopharynx	72
2.	Chalageri et al. [26] (2022)	India	Impact of Steam Inhalation, Saline Gargling, and Povidone-Iodine Gargling on Clinical Outcome of COVID-19 Patients in Bengaluru, Karnataka: A Randomized Control Trial	Open-labeled, parallel block, randomized controlled trial	21	80 I (n = 20) I ₂ (n = 20) I ₃ (n = 20)* c (n = 20)	RT-PCR	Nasopharynx	Not determined
3.	Guenezan et al. [27] (2021)	France	Povidone Iodine Mouthwash, Gargle, and Nasal Spray to Reduce Nasopharyngeal Viral Load in Patients With COVID-19: A Randomized Clinical Trial	Randomized clinical trial	7	24 I (n = 12) C (n = 12)	RT-PCR	Nasopharynx	48
4.	Amtha et al. [28] (2021)	Indonesia	PVP-I and Iota-Carrageenan Improve Subjective Clinical Symptoms In COVID-19 Emergency Hospital Wisma Atlet, Indonesia: A Single-Blind Randomized Clinical Trial	Single-blind, randomized clinical trial	14	89 I (n = 45) C (n = 44)	RT-PCR	Nasopharynx	Not determined

Appendix B

Table B1 presents a summary of the results of the quality assessment of randomized controlled studies and clinical trials using CONSORT 2010.

Table B1: CONSORT 2010 Checklist of Information to Include when Reporting a Randomized Trial

Section/Topic	Item No.	Checklist item	Reported on page No.			
			Domênico et al. [25] (2021)	Chalageri et al. [26] (2022)	Guenezan et al. [27] (2021)	Amtha et al. [28] (2021)
Title and abstract	1a	Identification as a randomised trial in the title	1	207	400	1659
	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstracts)	1	207	400	1659
Introduction Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	1;2	207;208	400	1659;1660
	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	2	208	400	1660
Methods Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	2	208	400	1660
	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	2	208	N/A	1660
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	3	208	400	1660
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	3	208	400	1661;1662
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	3	208	400;401	1661
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	3	208	400;401	1661
	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sample size	7a	How sample size was determined	3	208	400	1661
	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Randomisation:						
Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	4	208	N/A	1661
	8b	Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	2	208	N/A	1661

Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	N/A	208	N/A	N/A
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	3	208	400	1661
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how	3	208	N/A	1661
	11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	3	208	400;401	1661
Statistical methods	12a	Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	4	208;209	400;401	1662;1663
	12b	Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses	3;4	209;210;211	401	1662;1663;1664
Results Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	3	209	400;401	1663
	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	3	209	N/A	N/A
Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	2	209	401	1661;1663;1664
	14b	Why the trial ended or was stopped	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	4	210	400	1662;1663;1664
Numbers analysed	16	For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups	4	211	400	N/A
Outcomes and estimation	17a	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)	5	210	401	1664
	17b	For binary outcomes, the presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	5	210	401	1664
Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for	5	211	N/A	1662

		specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)				
Discussion Limitations	20	Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses	6	211	401	1665
Generalisability	21	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	6	211	401	1665
Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	6	211	401	1665
Other information Registration	23	Registration number and name of trial registry	2	208	400	1662;1666
Protocol	24	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available	2	N/A	400;401	N/A
Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	6	211	401	1666

Abbreviations: N/A, Not applicable

Appendix C

Figure 1: Article Search Mapping with the PRISMA 2020 Flowchart

Appendix D

Table 1: Characteristics of Research Subjects in Included Studies

Author (yrs)	Sex		Age range (yrs)	Comorbid disease			Exposure to COVID-19 n (%)	Respiratory and upper digestive symptoms (n (%))			
	M n (%)	F n (%)		Respiration n (%)	Diabetes n (%)	Hypertension n (%)		Anosmia	Non-productive cough	Dyspnea	Ageusia
Domênico et al. [25] (2021)	64 (60,4)	42 (39,6)	≤35 - ≥60	6 (5,7)	12 (11,3)	24 (22,6)	41 (38,6)	46 (43,40)	60 (31,08)	32 (16,58)	49 (25,39)
Chalageri et al. [26] (2022)	50 (62,5)	30 (38,5)	25-52,5	1 (1,25)	5 (6,25)	4 (5)	15 (18,8)	12 (18,46)	24 (36,92)	N/A	13 (20)
Guenezan et al. [27] (2021)	8 (33,33)	16 (66,67)	23-68	0 (0)	1 (8)	3 (25)	N/A	9 (37,5)	10 (41,67)	3 (12,5)	7 (29,17)
Amtha et al. [28] (2021)	67 (75,28)	22 (24,72)	19 - >40	N/A	N/A	N/A	39 (43,82)	29 (32,58)	23 (25,84)	12 (13,48)	20 (22,47)
TOTAL	189	110	-	7	17	31	95	96	117	47	89

Abbreviations: M, male; F, female; N/A, Not applicable

Appendix E

Table 2: Distribution of the Rate of Decline in Respiratory and Upper Digestive Symptoms Related to COVID-19

#	Author (yrs)	Patient group and treatment	Frequency and duration of drug use	Treatment time (day -)	Respiratory and upper digestive symptoms							
					Anosmia (%)	p	Non-productive cough (%)	p	Dyspnea (%)	p	Ageusia (%)	p
1.	Domênico et al. [25] (2021)	I*: H ₂ O ₂ 1% (n = 97)	3 times a day for 30s	0	41,3	0,2	52,4	0,8	16,5	<0,05 ^a	44,4	0,1
				6	34,6		27,3		5,16		35,7	
		C: placebo (distilled water with mint essence) (n = 96)		0	46,5	62,8	37,2	48,8				
				6	20,0	22,2	12,5	14,3				
2.	Chalageri et al. [26] (2022)	I: PVP-I 0,5% (n = 55)	3 times a day for 30s	0	32,88	0,1	17,80	0,05 ^a	N/A	N/A	16,44	0,1
		C: no intervention (n = 20)		21	0		0		0			
3.	Guenezan et al. [27] (2021)	I: PVP-I 1% (n = 12)	4 times a day	0	33	N/A	33	N/A	17	N/A	33	N/A
				7	0		0		0		0	
		C: no intervention (n = 12)		0	42	50	8	42				
				7	0	0	0	0				
4.	Amtha et al. [28] (2021)	I: PVP-I 1% (n = 45)	6 times a day	0	42,22	0,06	24,44	0,003 ^a	20	0,371 ^a	42,22	0,042 ^a
				14	2,22		2,22		0		2,22	
		C: COVID-19 standard treatment (n = 44)		0	25	29,55	6,82	25				
				14	0	0	0	0				

Abbreviations: I, Intervention; C, control; N/A, Not applicable; ^a = significant p-value

